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Impact of Sports Participation on Intrinsic Motivation and Academic Performance: The Mediating Role of Ethical Leadership and Parental Socialization

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of sports involvement on the intrinsic motivation and academic achievement of the students with special attention to the mediating effect of ethical leadership and parental socialization in tertiary institutions of higher education in Punjab, Pakistan. The study is affixed on assumption that participation in sports activities leads not only to physical but to psychological development, self-discipline and academic involvement. The quantitative survey design was adopted and data was collected from students who are studying in diverse institutions in the region. The research questions relationships between internal motivation, and positive learning behaviors as result of engaging in organized sports as well as examining how these relationships are reinforced by ethical leadership by coaches and positive parental practices. The results show that the involvement in sports positively affects intrinsic motivation and academic performance to considerable extent leading towards the desired determinations and leading outcomes. Thus, the results provide significant information for reaching desired and leading conclusion. The parental socialization is significant as it influences attitude of students through provision of emotional support, reinforcement of discipline and the encouragement of balanced attitude towards sports and academics. The synergistic effect of these mediators increases the overall sports participation effect on students' performance. The research paper also has implications to the existing body of literature by noting that the incorporation of sports programmes with ethical leadership conducts and parental participation is crucial in enhancing comprehensive development of student. The findings provide useful information to teachers, administrators and parents who want to enhance academic performance and motivation by using organized sports activities. All in all, the study highlights the fact that through the creation of conducive institutional and family conditions, best aspect of sports participation can be achieved when it comes to enhancing the educational value of this specific activity and the success of students in becoming the motivated, tough, and high-achievers. Thus, some recommendations and leading contributions were offered.

Keywords: Sports Participation, Ethical Leadership, Parental Socialization, Intrinsic Motivation, Academic Performance & Mediation

INTRODUCTION

There is general appreciation of the sports participation as the

major factor in growth of people and students. It affects many realms of life, among that is the intrinsic motivation as they will perform activities since it makes them feel satisfied and enjoy their lives [1]. This discusses the impacts of sports participation on intrinsic motivation and academic achievement with specific reference to mediating variables of ethical leadership and parental socialization [2]. The sports activities helpful in increasing intrinsic motivation as they help the person gain skills and bring pleasure. In this connection, personal interest is what drives intrinsic motivation as far as sports are concerned, and desire to attain personal objectives [3]. The sports involvement contributes to the accomplishment and fulfillment of the mastery of the innovative skills and struggle, which can be converted into the further motive victories in other spheres, such as success in academic and personal outcomes.

Sports and other regular physical activity have been linked with better academic performance and cognitive ability. The goal-setting in sports is capable of making students have the growth mindset that is useful in their academic work [4]. The sports activities teach time management and discipline that are applicable in academic environments. The workouts improve the brain, make them more focused, and eliminate stress, that may lead to improved grades [5]. Thus, the researchers have established positive correlation between sports activity and academic success. However, this relationship may be stronger and weaker depending on the level of involvement in sports and type of sport [6]. The students who are involved in sports tend to learn how to strike right balance between studies and sports. The ethical leadership refers towards leading others according to the ethical principles and values, encouraging fairness and integrity and respect for desired outcomes.

The leaders in sports can be respectable examples of ethics, which has an impact on the intrinsic motivation and academic achievement of students. The ethical leadership in sport context may exist in forms of coaches, teachers and role models who practice and exemplify ethical behavior [7]. The ethical leaders help and motivate, and this may boost the motivation and confidence of students. The students will internalize the ethical behavior and leadership when they see them, and capable of applying them to their academic and personal lives [8]. The parental socialization is the process where parents shape attitudes, behaviors and values, can have a positive influence on academic performance through provision of favorable learning and development environment [9].

This involves encouraging behaviours and attitude towards the sports and academics. This reinforcement be positive and it can spill over to academic life where the holistic approach to achievement is encouraged.

The parental encouragement to play sports may contribute to intrinsic motivation of students by encouraging and recognizing them that participate in open communication concerning the relevance of sports and academics may positively affect motivation and achievement of students in both fields [10]. Ethical leadership may complement values and behaviors fostered by parental socialization, forming ethical leadership and parental socialization may build enabling situation that improves intrinsic motivation and academic achievement of students [11]. The involvement in sports has positive effect on intrinsic motivation and academic success. The ethical leadership plays mediation roles that are vital in explaining this relation [12]. The knowledge of mediating role of ethical leadership, parental socialization relationship in mediating sports participation in relationships, motivation, academic performances led to interventions and programs aimed at students' developments.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is an attempt to explain the interaction between these factors to help in bringing an academic success and self-development to students. The leadership and parental socialization are important in mediating roles as offer support, guidance and reinforcement. The involvement in sporting activities boosts intrinsic motivation, which has positive influence on performance in schools [25]. The combination of factors has resulted in environment of support that promotes academic success and integration and a balance of measures to develop students [26]. This study investigates relationship between leadership and socialization sports participation, motivation and academic performance. The knowledge of such dynamics can bring the clue on how sports participation can shape academic personal leadership and family support play in process [27]. The sports activities have potential to impact different facets of student life like motivation and success in their lives.

The sports can instill teamwork, discipline and capacity to be resilient that can be applied into better academic performance and intrinsic motivation. This is motivation that is inspired by the rewards and personal nirvana. Intrinsic motivation is normally boosted by sports participation as a students get feeling of achievement, pleasure and personal development [28]. The

academic success and performance, as sports serve as intrinsic motivation that helps to attain improved academic performance because it boosts learning and perseverance [29]. The sport leaders and coaches, mentors. The ethical leadership in the sports environment improves the motivation and performance through establishing a positive impact on attitude and behaviour of parents toward their children [30]. The parental engagement and encouragement of students motivate and cares performance, attitude and support of sports and academic performance, and strengthening of effort and discipline.

The interrelations amid sports involvement, intrinsic motivation, academic performance, ethical leadership, and socialization of parents can be conceptualized based on a combined view on the basis of motivational and social theories. Sport participation offers students disciplined time to are then converted through stronger intrinsic motivation [4]. This implies that, being involved in sports does not work individually, rather it creates inner psychological conditions, which are carried over to educational performance [7]. Intrinsic motivation is key connecting factor amid sports involvement and academic achievement due to motivated students having higher chances of having goals and time management as well as staying attentive to learning activities [11]. By participating in frequent physical activities, the students will enjoy, feel competent, and have a sense of autonomy, these will strengthen their internal motivation to learn and succeed in their diverse research studies.

Studies indicate that intrinsic sport motivation encourages long-range participation in sporting activities and aids in encouraging positive experiences that stimulate persistence and dedication in other areas such as studies [14]. These connections are enhanced through ethical leadership to provide an atmosphere that supports positive values, justice, and ethical direction. Educational leaders like teachers, coaches, administrators who act ethically are able to increase engagement and prosocial motivation of students, who will internalize positive norms and take commitment towards sports and school work [15]. Research shows that participation in sporting activities boosts self-esteem and perseverance that ultimately leads to higher academic performance [18]. The regular training and competition teach students how to overcome adversity and challenges, control their emotions, and keep their attention on track; that can be applied towards desired academic environments.

RESULTS OF STUDY

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	SD
Sports Participation	338	1.30	4.80	3.3671	.74238
Intrinsic Motivation	338	1.70	4.70	3.4500	.70092
Ethical Leadership	338	1.33	4.67	3.2877	.83689
Parental Socialization	338	1.60	4.60	3.5703	.66691
Academic Performance	338	1.63	4.70	3.4711	.63840
Valid N (listwise)	338				

The descriptive analysis offers meaningful information in acquiring desired information about the demographic variables to offer comprehensive data to describe the variables of current study. The frequencies about the demographic attributes are self-explanatory whereas the descriptive statistics contains information about mean, minimum, maximum response rates and standard deviations to comprehend the description of research variables used in current research study. In this connection, the descriptive analysis in current study provides significant information in describing the variables.

H1: There is positive association amid the sports participation, intrinsic motivation, ethical leadership, parental socialization and academic performance (H1).

Correlations Analysis

Correlations

		[1]	[1]	[1]	[1]	[1]
Sports Participation	Pearson Correlation	1	.317**	.093	.303**	.457**
[1]	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.086	.000	.000
	N	338	338	338	338	338
Intrinsic Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.317**	1	.153**	.223**	.342**
[1]	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.005	.000	.000
	N	338	338	338	338	338
Ethical Leadership	Pearson Correlation	.093	.153**	1	-.005	.220**
[1]	Sig. (2-tailed)	.086	.005		.925	.000
	N	338	338	338	338	338

Parental Socialization [1]	Pearson Correlation	.303**	.223**	-.005	1	.369**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.925		.000
	N	338	338	338	338	338
Academic Performance [1]	Pearson Correlation	.457**	.342**	.220**	.369**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	338	338	338	338	338

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation procedures while determining the strength and direction through association was examined through correlation analysis to confirm the existence of relationships among the research variables under considerations. The results revealed that all the variables are significant and positively associated like sports participation and academic performance ($R = .457$ & $P = .000$), intrinsic motivation academic performance ($R = .342$ & $P = .000$), ethical leadership and academic performance ($R = .220$ & $P = .000$), parental socialization and academic performance ($R = .369$ & $P = .000$), which thus confirmed the existence of association and hypothesis was thus accepted from results of the correlation procedure and provide the clues towards the cause-&-effect relationships.

H2: There is positive significant impact of sports participation, intrinsic motivation, ethical leadership, and parental socialization on academic performance (H2).

Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	SEE
1	.570 ^a	.325	.317	.52765

Regression Analysis

ANOVA

Model		SS	DF	Mean Square	F	SIG.
1	Regression	44.632	4	11.158	40.076	.000 ^b
	Residual	92.713	333	.278		
	Total	137.345	337			

Regression Analysis

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	SE	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.811	.222		3.660	.000
	Sports Participation	.273	.042	.318	6.470	.000
	Intrinsic Motivation	.148	.044	.162	3.357	.001
	Ethical Leadership	.127	.035	.167	3.658	.000
	Parental Socialization	.227	.046	.237	4.957	.000

a. Predictors: Sports Participation, Parental, Ethical Leadership & Intrinsic Motivation

b. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

The regression procedure provides significant information about the cause-&-effect linkages in the research variables like sports participation, intrinsic motivation, ethical leadership, parental socialization and academic performance to confirm the prediction of academic performance over participation, intrinsic motivation, ethical leadership as well as parental socialization. Thus, the results show that there is 32.5% change in academic performance is due to sports participation, intrinsic motivation, ethical leadership, parental socialization with the significant and leading individual impact like sports participation ($\beta = .273$ & $P = .000$), intrinsic motivation ($\beta = .148$ & $P = .001$), ethical leadership ($\beta = .127$ & $P = .000$), and parental socialization ($\beta = .273$ & $P = .000$), which thus confirmed the desired prediction and hypothesis about the cause-&-effect linkages in therefore accepted.

H3: There is significant mediating role of the ethical leadership in relationship amid sports participation and academic performance (H3).

First Mediation Steps (a)

Model Summary

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	P
.0934	.0087	.6963	3.0691	1.0000	336.0000	.0807

Regression Coefficient

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.9332	.2022	14.5075	.0000	2.5355	3.3309
Sports	.1053	.0601	1.7519	.0807	-.0129	.2235

 Participation

Predicting Variable: Sports Participation

Criterion Variable: Ethical Leadership

Second & Third Mediation Steps (b & c)
Model Summary

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4905	.2406	.3113	58.1190	2.0000	335.0000	.0000

Regression Coefficient

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	1.7470	.1696	10.3026	.0000	1.4134	2.0805
Ethical Leadership	.1367	.0381	3.5848	.0004	.0617	.2118
Sports Participation	.3785	.0463	8.1737	.0000	.2874	.4696

Independent Variable: Sports Participation & Ethical Leadership

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

Fourth Mediation Step (c)
Model Summary

R	R-square	MSE	F	df1	df2	p
.4569	.2088	.3234	69.3454	1.0000	336.0000	.0000

Coefficient of Regression

Model	Coefficient	se	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	2.1481	.1643	13.0747	.0000	1.8249	2.4713
Sports Participation	.3929	.0472	8.3274	.0000	.3001	.4857

Independent Variable: Sports Participation

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance

The mediation procedure was used in this study to examine mediating role of ethical leadership in relationship amid sports participation and academic performance in determining the leading role of mediator in linking the independent and dependent variables of study to extract desired information and reaching the conclusion that whether it is partial mediation or full mediation in the current research study. The mediation procedure provides significant information about the research variables through four different paths of mediation in determining the direct as well as indirect relationships among the research issues under study. In this linking, mediation results in current study provide significant information that confirmed the partial mediating role of the ethical leadership in relationship between sports participation and academic performance due to decrease in coefficient value from (.3929) in direct relationship to (.3785) in the indirect links and

hypothesis about the mediation was partially accepted from the results and outcomes of the mediation procedure.

DISCUSSION

The leaders in sports can be respectable examples of ethics, which has an impact on the intrinsic motivation and academic achievement of students. The ethical leadership in sport context may exist in forms of coaches, teachers and role models who practice and exemplify ethical behavior [7]. The ethical leaders help and motivate, and this may boost the motivation and confidence of students. The students will internalize the ethical behavior and leadership when they see them, and capable of applying them to their academic and personal lives [8]. The parental socialization is the process where parents shape attitudes, behaviors and values, can have a positive influence on academic performance through provision of favorable learning and development environment [9]. This involves encouraging behaviours and attitude towards the sports and academics. This reinforcement be positive and it can spill over to academic life where the holistic approach to achievement is encouraged.

Academic achievement may be promoted by open communication between parents and students on significance of balancing between sport and academic activities since it offers the supportive system of academic success [22]. This consistency can be used to increase intrinsic motivation of students by offering them consistent and supportive feedback on the significance of effort and achievement. The ethical leaders and permissive parents make difference in environment where athletic and academic success are appreciated [23]. Sports involvement and ethical leadership go hand in hand contribute to whole person development are in tandem they formulate a unified support system that fosters academic achievement, intrinsic motivation, academic performance, ethical leadership, parental socialization are interconnected [24]. Thus, leadership that follows the code of ethics can give direction and motivation to match the gains of sports to attain better scores in academic tasks.

The sports can instill teamwork, discipline and capacity to be resilient that can be applied into better academic performance and intrinsic motivation. This is motivation that is inspired by the rewards and personal nirvana. Intrinsic motivation is normally boosted by sports participation as a students get feeling of achievement, pleasure and personal development [28]. The academic success and performance, as sports serve as intrinsic motivation that helps to attain improved academic performance

because it boosts learning and perseverance [29]. The sport leaders and coaches, mentors. The ethical leadership in the sports environment improves the motivation and performance through establishing a positive impact on attitude and behaviour of parents toward their children [30]. The parental engagement and encouragement of students motivate and cares performance, attitude and support of sports and academic performance, and strengthening of effort and discipline.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The institutions need to help boost and enhance athletic programs by incorporating them within the academic support systems where the students are offered a chance to engage in physical activities that help motivate them, instill discipline and academic stimulation in institutions.
2. The parents should be actively engaged by awareness programs, frequent communication with schools in a bid to encourage their children to take up sports besides upholding the positive attitude towards learning, responsibility, and time management at home toward desired leading outcomes.
3. Ethical leadership should be encouraged in schools and universities, coaches, teachers, and administrators should be trained to lead fairly, supportive direction to observe an environment that reinforces values and motivates students to transfer sports experiences to academic achievements.
4. To enhance intrinsic motivation and academic achievement, policymakers and education leaders need to come up with policies that promote collaboration amid schools, families, and communities to develop promising ecosystems, which maximize the developmental rewards of sports participation.

DIRECTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

1. The longitudinal designs be considered in future studies that will allow determining how the long-term effects of sports participation on intrinsic motivation and academic achievement be observed and how roles of ethical leadership and parental socialization change with stages of education.
2. There should be comparative studies in other cultural, regional, and institutional settings to establish whether or not relationships observed differ among the various educational systems and social settings. These are required for completing the different tasks as well leading desired consequences.
3. It is advised that researchers should examine more mediating and moderating factors including the peer influence, school climate, psychological wellbeing, and socioeconomic factors so as to have a

more holistic view of the mechanisms behind sports engagement and academic performance.

4. The mixed-method techniques, such as qualitative interviews and observations, could be used in future research to obtain more understanding of the experiences of students, parents, and educators in terms of sports participation, ethical leadership, and process of socialization in families.

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